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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“LEARNINGS FROM MY MASTERAL EDUCATION ONLINE CLASS (SCHOOL ORGANIZATION, ADMINISTRATION AND SUPERVISION)”

To enhance my professional competence, improve my knowledge and skills and meet the growing professional demand of the department of education I decided to pursue my graduate studies and get my master's degree. Bearing in mind that through this action I can make myself relevant, appropriate, and can contribute meaningfully to the attainment of the educational goal and in the improvement of the teaching and learning process in the country.

One of my subjects is School Organization, Administration and Supervision (ED205), with the guidance of my professor OLIVER E. ORTIZ JR. and the valuable sharing's and informative discussions of each reporters of various topics in this course, I was able to; identify different theories and principle of school organization and administration, learn different leadership strategies to improve administrative and learning outcomes, develop effective management practices, and acquire knowledge in managing school challenges. These learnings help me become a better educator and it provides valuable insights and lessons that can be applied in the school context. It enhances my views and perception on management and supervision particularly on school leadership and supervision, financial and resource management, and in school governance and community relations.

This experience provides me with satisfaction and happiness, satisfied in the sense that I've got what I need and happiness for what I gained in attending this class, for meeting other educators dreaming of becoming a school leader someday and for sharing with them my relative experiences on this matter. It also boosts my confidence and self-belief to do more and overcome different educational challenges. It gives me extra motivation to make a difference and be a game changer in improving the quality of service in the field of education.

Furthermore, this help me understand that true essence of being a school leader is not just about leading people or performing different administrative tasks or functions but to make sure that you care for the people and make them believe that they are part of the institution that they must be involved in every school planning and preparation and recognize how important they are in achieving the desired learning outcomes.

This made me realize that there is no perfect education system, however, with great leaders and good governance guided by the true spirit of public service with highest degree of integrity and honesty, the educational goal will surely be achieved.

With this, it is my honor to share and apply all these learnings to the whole school community, and serve them with dignity and pride.

